

ANALYSIS OF PRAGMATIC IMPLICATURES OF AESTHETICS IN ADVERTISING

Ikedieze Charles Enyinnaya¹
Philomena Effiong Umoren²

¹Department of linguistics
Kingsley Ozumba Mbadiwe University,
Imo State, Nigeria
dimgbaike368@gmail.com

²Departement of Mass Communication
Philomenaumoren@aksu.edu.ng
Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus

ABSTRACT

Advertising is one of the application areas of communication design. It is a way of communication that aims to attract people's attention to product, service, organization and change of their views and attitudes about it in the desired direction. The essence of communication in discourse, whether spoken or written is that it should elicit some response from the speaker or writer. At times one wonders why people do not behave in conformity with the message intended by writing or speaking. Could it be due to the non-adherence of communication to certain pragmatic, syntactic and semantic rules among other things? It is on this basis that this paper focuses on the analysis of pragmatic implicatures of aesthetics in advertising; as aesthetic in advertising is a metaphoric expression conveyed through visual representation and linguistic form. It is primarily aimed at ascertaining the extent of adherence of Television commercials to Grice (1975) Maxims of Cooperative Principle (CP). The study reveals that the strength of the Cooperative Principle lies in the distinction between the Gricean Maxims. The paper concludes that CP is important to our understanding of advertising communication embedded in aesthetic; because it enables us to know why communication spoken or written quite often fails, and how it can be more successful. Therefore, this paper suggests that Television Commercial writers should always note that informativeness is what the public desires; if Television Commercial should be rated as being packaged well.

KEYWORDS: Pragmatic Implicature, Aesthetics, and Metaphoric

INTRODUCTION

Aesthetic work appeals to or sensitizes any or combination of our senses or taste. Every aesthetic work must cause people to feel and experience what the artist has felt and experienced. As soon as the listeners or viewers, or even spectators are affected by the same feelings which the artist felt, experience has been clarified and intensified; thus aesthetic communication has been experienced. Aesthetic is the study of the mind and emotions in relations to the sense of beauty. If we put aesthetics – emotion on scale we will have some responses like, attractive, not attractive, desirable, not desirable, arousing, not arousing, and beautiful, not beautiful. Any response in the positive is regarded as aesthetics – emotional in relation with the perception of a media production (Nnanyelugo, 2013). There are many elements that are employed to bring aesthetics in media production. Radio production makes use of mood, human voice, time and sound effects: Television production makes use of light, sound, emotion and space. All these elements, if employed professionally will result into excellent products which will attract marvels from even the most critical listeners or viewers.

Aesthetic is commonly known as the study of the mind and emotions in relation to sense of beauty. Scholars in the field of sociology define it as a critical reflection on art, culture and nature. Aesthetic deals with motions such as the beauty, the ugly, the sublime, or the comic as applicable to the fine arts. Aesthetic judgments involve many issues. They can be culturally conditioned, linked to emotions and at least partly intellectual and interpretative. Aesthetic is the philosophic branch of inquiry concerned with beauty, art and perception. From its philosophic roots in ancient Greece, where thinkers like Socrates and Plato considered the inherent meaning and beauty of things, aesthetics is also used to refer to the critique of art and design.

Consumers' involvement and response to advertising messages may be mediated not only by the information content of the messages but by advertisement format as well. Aesthetics response to stimulus is suffused with emotion and also extends beyond emotion to include evaluative reactions to an object. This is a common, socialized response tendency that applies to advertisement components (Christian, 2009). Consumers we believe, are culturally conditioned to equate visual messages with art, beauty and emotional attraction. Consumers' response to advertisement is due to the utilitarian quality of a product as well as aesthetic features of a product. The aesthetic-emotional scales consist of four (4) objective pairs: attractive/not attractive, desirable/not desirable, arousing/not arousing, and beautiful/not beautiful.

Affirmative responses to adjective of these types are characteristically regards as aesthetic/emotional in content within our culture. Therefore, consumers aesthetic sense would be more activated by visual imagery, as all-visual advertisements would be rated along the line of more attractive, desirable arousing, and beautiful. Advertisers focus on aesthetics to target and appeal to their audience. Numerous television shows feature attractive people. The idea is the more attractive the person in the advertisement the more likely the viewer is to want to be like them.

Television advertisement is dependent on product aesthetic strategy. For example, if an advertisement is selling something to help with depression, it may feature a more average looking person to whom the viewer can relate. Advertisement is communication whose purpose is to inform potential customers about products and services and how to use and obtain them. Advertisement plays an important role. A smart customer always possesses the basic knowledge about the product before going to shop due to the advertisement and the effectiveness of the advertisement would lie in the fact if all the expectations of the customers are being fulfilled. The expectations are aroused by aesthetics. More interesting interface increase consumers of advertisement product arousal and sustain their interest and effectiveness (Odebunmi, 2007). Aesthetic is a strong determinant of pleasure experiences by consumer. Social psychology has it that physical attractiveness is associated with a wide range of socially desirable characteristics. Perceptions of usability are also affected by perceptions of aesthetics. Consumer product involvement is as an important variable that is taken into consideration in advertising. This product involvement influences the buyers/users decisions and information seeking processes. A much cherished product is influenced by the product type and consumers motivational level by aesthetically packaged advertisement. Any aesthetics element not well featured in advertisement production can reduce the value of the advertisement.

Aesthetic in media is so important because it is a compilation/synthesis of several genres of art and information delivery. New media have opened the flood gate for advertisers to inject high art into advertising hence the blending of art and advertising. How does one define the aesthetic of the new media? New media have been able to create new aesthetic that placed form and function on equal planes. Such advertising aesthetic of form and function is seen these days both in new media and non-new media advertising. Integration of art and advertising seem to be the order of the day. Advertisement is communication whose purpose is to inform potential customers about products and services, how to use and obtain them. The objective of this paper is to analyze the pragmatic implicatures of aesthetics in advertising.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Aesthetic in advertisement is like pervasive technique used by advertisers in advertisement production. The analysis of advertisement aesthetics will equip consumers better to make better decisions about products of their interest. Advertisement is a communication whose purpose is to inform potential customers about products and services and how to use and obtain them. According to the article of Bitner (1992) consumers judge the environment and stimuli according to aesthetic. Media aesthetics examines the meaning of visual images designed for use in film and electronic media. Aesthetic refers to the study of sensory values. This means the judgment or evaluation by the senses and through time, it has come to refer to critical or philosophical thought about art, culture and or nature. Aesthetic is interested in ways of seeing and of sensing the world. It involves ways of seeing and perceiving the world as well as new and novel interpretations.

Aesthetic is the philosophical branch of inquiry concerned with beauty, art and perception. Aesthetics from its philosophic roots in ancient Greece where thinkers like Solon and Plato considered the inherent meaning and beauty of things; aesthetics is also used to refer to the critique of art and design. The word aesthetics derives from the ancient Greek word, *aisthanomi*, which means perception by the sense. As such, it is used in modern English as a noun, in the sense that something can appeal to the sense. In a contemporary sense, aesthetics can be used, to reference a particular style or design for example, a culture that used a motif through many areas of design and function can be said to appreciate or adhere to a specific aesthetic.

Aesthetics are an integral part of the human experience least as a perception of beauty and art whether or not one develops a thorough understanding of aesthetic as philosophy; we encounter objects of beauty and perceive them as such. Owums (2007) asserts that there are various approaches through which a research can be conducted. That aesthetic appreciation of a programme requires content analysis. Content analysis is a research approach, used in the determination of issues related to specific programme content in broadcast medium. Aesthetic value is culture-bound, whereas aesthetic experience (sense perception) is a possibility for all normal human beings Emmanuel Akpan (1990). The extent to which aesthetic is realized varies with individuals according to where they are or have been and their general psychological ecology or life space. The type of product advertised, and the interest level of individual matters in aesthetic appreciation of an advertisement. This is because we only feel what we know. Aesthetic that deals with value limits its concern to understanding beauty, appreciating beauty, and judging beauty with a certain degree of consistency. This is concept of aesthetic in relation to good and sweetness.

Zettl views aesthetics as an attempt to master certain sense perceptions and a demonstration of their mastery in the interpretation of our daily experiences effectively through any medium of communication, for a given audience, give, as we perceive advertisement every day. This interest goes beyond a culture's way of looking at beauty and assumes that as humans we would all cry if pricked, and laugh if well stimulated. Aesthetic experience is a universal experience for everyone who is emotionally sensitive. What we need, in every communication medium is one knowledgeable enough in the art of ordering clarification and intensification of experiences to turn the routine into interesting account. This is why advertisers should package advertisement in good aesthetic manner. As vision is an aesthetic element in television, for a television commercial to arouse the interest of consumer, advertisers should use words to create images in the minds of the audience. Radio, television and film all share the aesthetic element of sound. Sound as aesthetic element includes the human voice, sound effect, and music. In presenting programmes the voice can be consciously manipulated to produce communication that affects the mind of the audience member (Emmanuel Akpan, 1990). Sound effects can create a feeling of reality in an advertisement. Film and television rely on light for their operation. Zettl notes the basic lighting purposes to include manipulation of the perception of our environment. Advertiser

can make the consumers feel the way he went through the way he manipulates their perception. Proper manipulation of the sequence, scene and shot, times have some aesthetic functions. Time when properly controlled the viewer can experience a dynamic rhythm in what he is viewing. Television commercials can be executed in a variety of ways that include the following: commercial testimonials vignettes and lifestyle (Ozoh, 1998). Problems and solution could serve as a strategy and aesthetic way to persuade consumers to buy an advertised product. The problem is usually first shown to exist and to be highly disturbing and then use of the brand leads to a solution. Testimonial format is another way of TV advertising. The testimonial format features the endorser endorsing the quality of the product or the satisfaction derived from its usage (Ozoh 1998). Advertising is directed for group of people not individuals, hence it is non-personal. It could be to the youths. It could be to adults or the aged. It is also not face-to-face communication (Okunna 2002). This is why advertisement requires being packaged aesthetically to arouse feeling for the product for services advertised. Television as a broadcast medium presents cultural developments in the most graphically imaginable manner that affects the human psyche and excite aesthetic appreciation (Owuamaslan 2006). The concept of synchronization ensures that perfection is made for sound and actions in broadcasting. It is the principle of blending appropriate artistic elements in a creative production that gives rise to synchronization.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Evolving a theory or theories that serve as the platform which scholarly works are forged is a traditional practice. This paper is therefore, not averse to this tradition. Consequently the theories of uses and gratification Environment, Cultivation come handy.

Environmental theory presupposes three key issues in communication.

- a. That the media not only affects in environment but messages that emanate from the environment.
- b. The channel of transmission is more important than the message content.
- c. Just as it affects the environment, in the same way, the environment affects the media by determining the media that is suitable to it. For example, if the advertising message from the banking institution is dealing with large and illiterate customers of audience, we should not think of using the print media. The environment determines what media the advertising agents should use. The theory presupposes that the advertisers who serve as the media should be mirroring the other means of knowing about the world. The basic idea behind cultivation theory analysis is that heavy television viewing cultivates perception of the reality line with view and advertising messages presented in television programmes. This theory explain why the adverts messages sent to the audience by the banking industries for an instance through the mass media, especially to the television audience will cultivate the perception of the reality and make them to believe the advertising message and also convince them to patronize such advertising production and services.

The uses and gratification theory explains the reason why level of media influence or effect on the individual greatly influences the individuals choice of advertising product and

services. Any advertising message and service that is normally meeting the national need, performs some form of utilitarian function on individual's uses of such advertising message. In other word the level of gratification an individual derives from an advertising message vis-a-vis media is proportionally related to the individual's preference of such advertising message through such medium.

Environment as it is could be the immediate environment or the larger society. The advertising media must be product of the environment if the advertising media must function well, it must reflect the environment. The bottom line of uses and gratification theory is that media do not do things to people rather people to things with media. Specifically the objectives, according to Burgeon, Hunsaker and Dawson (1994) are to explain how individuals use mass communication to gratify their needs as they stay up late at night to watch the local news or read a medium. In their contribution, Baran and Davis (2001) conclude that audience members actively seek out the mass media to satisfy individual needs. These include learning, passing time, and companionship escape from tension excitement and for relaxation. To Baran (2002) and Devito (1991) mass media audience make outlive use of whatever, the media have to offer.

Mcqnaril (2005) adds that the media serve the various needs of the society, which include cohesion cultural continuity of public information of all kinds. This pre-supposes that individual also use media for related purposes such as personal guidance relaxation adjutancy information and identity formation. Cultivation media theory stresses the capacity of the media to make people change their behavior and change to new ways of life. Cultivation theory was propounded by Gerber, gross, Signorelli and Morgan (1980) they asserts that mass media especially television exerts on tremendous influence by altering individuals perception of reality. This theory assumes that the more time people spend watching television, the more their world view will be like those spread by televisions.

Okonwa (2002) observes the televisions viewers dominate are symbolic environment” substitutes its message about reality for personal experience. According to lacndiberg and huller (1968) the uses and gratification theory rests on several assumptions.

- 1) The audience being active seeks specific type of media content to satisfy its needs.
- 2) People select their media force from a cafeteria of all kind of offering. Including selecting from competing media as well as from different move conventional and more traditional modes of needs fulfillment.
- 3) People are sufficiently aware of how the media satisfy their needs, interest, and are articulate enough to verbalize this.
- 4) Audience use of the media should be explored without making value judgments about the cultural significance of their mass media consumption behavior.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Aesthetics, according to the oxford advanced learning's dictionary is concerned with beauty and of things. Here creativity and professionalism most come to bear. If certain elements, in creative work are not handled well in programmes production audience appeal

will be eroded. Grice's (1975) maxims of Cooperative Principles asserts that as humans, we are social beings and when we talk, we usually talk with or to other unless we do a monologue. In other words speakers tend to be cooperative when they talk. Cooperative here means that the speaker knows that each utterance is a potential inference in personal right and wishes. This is why the advertiser should write the advert script in consonance with people's wellbeing. To this effect Grice put up four maxims to follow while in conversation with others, as cooperative principles. Maxim of quality: We are to tell the truth or something that is provable. Maxim of quantity: We have to be informative as required, we should not say more or less. Maxim of relation: Our response has to be relevant to the discussion. Maxim of manner: we have to avoid ambiguity or obscurity; we should be direct and straight forward. How we say what we say matters in communication.

RESULTS

Advertisement: is communication whose purpose is to inform potential customers about products and services, how to use and obtain them. Every major medium is used to deliver these messages including television, radio, movies, magazines, newspapers and internet. Advertisement influences our lives in many unsuspecting ways because of rapid changes in the macro environment.

How do media houses create aesthetic features in advertisement production?

Advertising is regarded as a paid form of non-personal presentation of ideas, goods and services by an identified sponsor. Testing or evaluation of advertising effectiveness refers to the managerial exercise aimed at relating the advertising results to the established standards of performance. It is an attempt to know whether the message designed properly has reached the greatest member of prospects. Television is the youngest, glamorous and highly specialized as it provides scientific synchronization of sound light, motion, colour and immediacy. These television features contribute to the aesthetic packaging of programme. People may be conscious of advertising when they watch television, but advertising in its many forms pervades society, invades households, and persuades mind nearly every waking moment. Advertising is everywhere, but nowhere is it more apparent than television screen. Advertising agency need to create commercials for their clients that stand out from the rest of commercial, hence the need for aesthetic. There advertisement must communicate to their clients message more clearly and be better remembered than the middle of mediocrity that exist among most advertisements. The advertisement must have punch, as to stop the viewer from changing the channel. For any advertisement to make impact, it must be packaged aesthetically. The importance of advertising is steadily on the increase in modern society. Just as the media of social communication, themselves have enormous influence everywhere, so advertising using media as its vehicle is a pervasive, powerful force shaping attitudes and behavior in today's world. Introduction of new technologies, most importantly internet, has injected high art into advertising. This is aesthetic in its height. Take for an instance Nike and its advertising agency that have broken the mold for golf advertising and created new

aesthetic that placed form and function on equal planes. This advertisement was released in 2006 and since then almost all golf, companies have bought into Nike advertising aesthetic of form and function both in new media and non-new media advertising. This was done as gains what one normally found before in golf advertising where advertisement is riddled with specifications quotations from the famous professional golfers and some meaningless jargon and specification. Another aesthetic move made by Nike that attract audience more these days, are several selectable camera angles that interchange seamlessly without stopping the video. The different camera angles combined the sound video and text. Some camera angles focus on artistic angle and some on advertising.

The major goal of any communication activity is to influence the consciousness and behavior of the message encoder and decoder to the extent that the decoder responds with feedback to the sender. Aesthetic work is to appeal to, or sensitize any or a combination of the sense or taste. Every aesthetic work must cause people to feel and experience what the artist felt and experienced. Aesthetic elements are very essential as air to humans in advertisement production. For example, music as aesthetic element is capable of making people happy and can produce feelings and sensations. If properly used in advertisement production can add beauty, as it is used to catch the consumers' attention. In television, production light is the first aesthetic element to be mentioned lighting in television is meant to provide the television camera, with adequate illumination for technically acceptable pictures. To make advertisement production effective lighting should be properly used. When we have unintended silhouettes as result of poor lighting beauty is lost in advertisement production. Without sound as aesthetic element and excellently presented picture, advertisement will be mute and less aesthetically meaningful. When sound as an aesthetic value on television is projected with uniformity of action, it makes production effective. Television is a word economic medium as sound complements pictures, to this end when time as aesthetic element is employed in advertisement production to portray a given period as in fast motion and slows motion beauty of a programme is enhanced. Space on its part is an aesthetic factor on television in that when light creates an image there must be a medium for the light to reflect on or register what it has seen. It suffices to say here that aesthetic features add to the effectiveness of advertisement production. That with good aesthetics value, there will be good deal of appeal to people.

Do Advertisers take the public into consideration bearing in mind the cooperative nature of communication in their advert production?

The importance of utterance in discourse whether spoken or written is that it should elicit some response from the listener. At times we wonder why people do not behave in conformity with the message intended by the speaker or writer. Could it be due to the non-adherence of communication to certain pragmatic, syntactic and semantic rules among other things? It is on that basis this paper focuses on the analysis of pragmatic implicatures of aesthetics in two television commercials using Grice (1975) Maxims of cooperative. In trying

to create aesthetic the advertisers violate some maxims. The cooperative principle is important to our understanding language use in the society because it enables us to know why communication, spoken or written often fails. The success or failure of an advert to achieve desired result depends on the language and visuals involved. That is whether the writer takes the public into consideration bearing in mind the cooperative nature of the communication. Davis (2005) sees pragmatic implicatures as the act of meaning or implying one thing by saying something else. This paper sees this as aesthetics in advertising done in figurative expressions.

Metaphor in Advertising pertains to graphics that associate a thing or person, concept or idea in something else other than what it normally means. Therefore, aesthetics here is something left implicit just to persuade audience. Grice (1975) uses the term implicature to account for what a speaker can imply, suggest or mean as distinct from what the speaker literally says. Conversational implicature is subsumed to mean an implication or suggestion deduced from the point of an utterance. Whether the advertiser takes the public into consideration bearing in mind the cooperative nature of communication is the basis of this study as this paper analyses two television commercials. This analysis is on the premise that the evaluation of the Commercial is made explicit using Grice's maxims of cooperative principles(CP).

The two Television commercials selected for this analysis are: Old Spice and Nike. The taglines of these commercials were copied and analyzed. The Maxims of cooperative principles were propounded in 1975 by a philosopher of language called Paul H.P. Grice. He argues that all speakers regardless of their cultural background adhere to a basic principle governing conversation which he termed the cooperative principle. That is we assume that in conversation the participants will cooperate with each other when making their conversations.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

“The Man Your Man Could Smell Like” is a commercial contributed by Old Spice body wash that targets men. The commercial tries to persuade men into buying their product. Looking at the tagline “The man your man could smell like” This is metaphorical, and violates the maxim of quality, which requires the Advertiser to write only what he believes to be true and have evidence. The statement attests to the Advertiser's insincerity. How true is it that the looks of the man portrays smell that any lady would perceive as the smell of her desired man. In other words is sense of smell in the looks? The Maxim of quantity is also violated. The information is less than what is required or necessary. Does using Old Spice body wash turn one to athletic perfect man as portrayed? Is the way he talks and uses his tone very smooth and flirtatious as result of the use of Old Spice body wash? The Advertiser has employed brevity in the name of aesthetics at the expense of clarity which adversely affected communication or message intended. There is the violation of the maxim of manner. The advert to some extent is obscure. Is the advert saying that using Old Spice body wash leads to

riding on white horse, or everyone that uses the body wash should be riding on white horse as mark of smelling good? The message is not intelligible in the sense of conveying the intended illocutionary goal to the public' Nike is a famous athletics sport wear company. "Just Do it" is tagline in the company's advert released first in 1988 featuring 80 year old man telling about how he runs 17 miles every morning.

The advert violates the maxim of quality. How true is it that by wearing Nike product you can run 17 miles every day even at the age of 80 years. Does it mean that you live up to 80 years if you use Nike product? There is violation of manner. Even though the writer has maintained orderliness void of repetition expression, "Just Do It" is figuratively used just for aesthetic reason. An average reader might not understand it. So, clarity is not achieved as expressed. How what is said is to be said is not considered by the advertiser.

CONCLUSION

From the analysis of two Television Commercials based on Grice's Maxims of Cooperative Principle, it is observed that the strength of the Cooperative Principle lies in the distinction between the sense of an utterance and its force. The illocutionary force of an utterance cannot be accounted for by semantic rules, but in the totality of arousal from metaphoric expression conveyed through visual representation and linguistic form as aesthetic implication. It is deducible that most Television commercials tend to violate Grice's Maxims. In trying to create aesthetics violate Grice's Maxims. In attempting to give information up to the required measure Television commercials may be violating the maxim of quality. Violation can be quietly or openly done. Advert writers at times flout the maxim of quantity by giving little information so as to arouse the interest of the public towards that which is advertised or to keep the public in suspense.

This paper as well promotes the notion that advertisement has an aesthetic dimension. Television commercial aesthetic is created through metaphoric expression conveyed through visual representation and linguistic form. Manipulation of sequence scene, shots and lighting have aesthetic functions. The creation process of advertisement is a two layered designed process that consists of the creation of the image/visual (form) and meaning (content).

RECOMMENDATION

1. Advertiser should be more creative about ideas that are translated to advertisement meant to satisfy thirst of consumer.
2. There is nothing intrinsically good or intrinsically evil about advertising. It is a tool, an instrument it can be used well and it can be used badly. It can have and sometimes does have beneficial result, it can and often, have a negative, harmful impact on individuals and society, hence the need for proper aesthetics packaging of advertisement.
3. Utterly useless goods are touted to the public, if false assertions are made about goods for sales, if less than admirable human tendencies are exploited aesthetically, those responsible for such advertising harm society and forfeit their goods, name and

credibility. Aesthetics purgation to buy articles of luxury can arouse false wants that hurt both individuals and families by making them ignore what they really need. Those forms of advertising which, without same, exploit the sexual instincts as aesthetics simply to make money or which seek to penetrate into the subconscious recesses of the mind in a way that threatens the freedom of the individual must be shunned.

4. Advertising can betray its role as a source of information by misrepresentation and by withholding relevant facts. Sometimes, too, the information function of media can be subverted by advertiser's pressure upon publication or programmed not to treat question that might prove embarrassing or inconveniencing, this kind of advertisement is covered up with aesthetics form. There should be a check for this kind of advertisement
5. Advertising is often aesthetically packaged not simply to inform but to persuade and motivate to convince people to act in certain ways buy certain products or services patronize certain institutions, and the like. This is where particular abuses can occur. There should be a control to check such abuses that can result from such advertisement
6. The practice of "brand" related advertising can raise serious problems. Often there are only negligible differences among similar products of different brands, and advertising may attempt to more people to act on the basis of irrational motives (i.e. brand loyalty) by status, fashion, sex appeal aesthetics, instead of presenting differences in product quality and price as basis for rational choice. This should be guarded against in advertisement packaging

REFERENCE

- Aina, S (2004) *Intermediate News Writing and Reporting*. Abeokuta: Julian Publishers
- Akpan, E. and Etuk, U. (1990) *Aesthetics Philosophical and Artistic Dimensions* Uyo: Modern Business Press Ltd.
- Bran, J. (2002) *Introduction to Mass Communication Literacy and Culture*. USA: McGraw – Hill Books.
- Christian, J. L. (2009) *Philosophy: An Introduction to Art of Wondering*. California: Wadsworth Language Learning
- Grice, P. (2012) *Cooperative Principles*. Retrieved from <http://awinlanguage.blogspot.com>
- Mc Quail, D. (2009) *Mc Quail's Communication Theory*. (6th Edition) London: Sage Publications.
- Nnanyelugo O.(2013) *The Business of Advertising*. Benedette Publishers, 105 Adeniran Ogunsanya Road, Surulere, Lagos, Nigeria
- Odebunmi, A. (2007) *Advertisement in English: An Ethnolinguistic Tool in Sociolinguistics in the Nigerian Context* vol.1 edited by Dele Adeyanju. Ileife: Obafemi Awolowo Press.
- Onabajo, O. (2004) *Introduction to Broadcasting*. Lagos: Gabi Concept Limited.
- Okunna, S. (2002) *Teaching Mass Communication: A Multi:- Dimensional Approach*. Enugu: New Generational Books.
- Ozoh, H. (1998) *Principle and Practice of Advertising*. Lagos: Nelag and Co. Ltd.

- Owuamalam, E. (2006) Introduction to Broadcasting Nigeria: Top Class Agencies Ltd.
- Owuamalam, E. (2007) Radio- TV Production. Nigeria: Image and Slogans Consultants Ltd.
- Zettl H. (2005) Sight, Sound Motion: Applied Media Aesthetics (Fourth Edition). Australia: Thomason Wadsworth.